

SHODANOTTARA SHAMANA CHIKITSA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF SWITRA (VITILIGO): A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Background: Switra is described in Ayurvedic classics under Kushta Roga and is characterized by white discoloration of the skin. It is primarily associated with vitiation of Bhrajaka Pitta along with Vata Dosha and involvement of Rakta, Mamsa, and Meda Dhatus. In contemporary dermatology, Switra can be correlated with vitiligo, a chronic depigmenting disorder affecting approximately 1–2% of the global population, attributed to autoimmune destruction of melanocytes.

Objective: To evaluate the efficacy of Shodanottara Shamana Chikitsa in the management of Switra. **Methods:** A 38-year-old male patient presenting with depigmented macules over the glabellar region and lips was treated with a combination of Samshodhana, Amapachana, Shamana, and Bahirparimarjana therapies. Internal medications included Panchatikta Guggulu Ghrita, Eranda Taila, Arogyavardhini Vati, Tiktamrita capsules, and Bakuchi capsules. External application of Bakuchi Lepa

with Gomutra and Vencose gel was advised. **Results:** After 15 days of treatment, hyperpigmentation was observed over the glabellar lesion followed by desquamation and gradual restoration of normal skin color. The response was slower over the lip region. **Conclusion:** Early-stage Switra (Nava and Alpa Pramana) responds favorably to integrated

Shodhana and Shamana therapies. Adherence to Pathya Ahara-Vihara and Yoga plays a crucial supportive role in management.

KEY WORDS: Swithra, Vitiligo, Nithya virechana, Shamana chikitsa, Case report.

INTRODUCTION

Switra is described in Ayurvedic literature under Kushta Roga Chikitsa and is characterized by Shweta Varna (white discoloration) of the skin. Bhrajaka Pitta, located in the skin, governs complexion (Chaya) and radiance (Prabha). Its vitiation, along with Vata Dosha, leads to Twak Vaivarnya^[1] (discoloration). The pathology predominantly involves Meda Dhatu, with varying clinical presentations depending on the affected Dhatu: Rakta Dhatu involvement – Reddish patches, Mamsa Dhatu involvement – Copper-colored patches, Meda Dhatu involvement – White patches.^[2]

In modern medicine, Switra is correlated with Vitiligo, a chronic depigmenting disorder characterized by well-demarcated, symmetrical, non-inflammatory macules. It affects 1–2% of the global population, with nearly one-third of cases beginning in childhood. The condition is considered autoimmune in nature, involving T-cell-mediated destruction of melanocytes.^[3]

OBJECTIVE

To evaluate the efficacy of Shodanottara Shamana Chikitsa in the management of Switra.

CASE REPORT

A 38-year old male patient presented on the OPD of Karnataka ayurveda medical college Mangalore with complaints of Gradual development of whitish patches over the glabellar region (Bhrumadhya) and both lips for one year which is characterized by symmetrically distributed Epidermal macules without itching & discharge. Initially he developed over glabellar region later over both lips. there is a positive family history & since his Paternal uncle responded well to Ayurvedic treatment the patient opted for Ayurveda as the primary modality.

Personal History

Patient is middle-class school Teacher Two years prior to presentation, he was unmarried & living away from his family due to occupational commitments during this period, he frequently consumed outside food. Dietary history revealed regular intake of curd, particularly at night.^[4] He also reported the incompatible dietary practice of consuming fish

along with curd & frequent consumption of Kulattha, Mamsa ahara,^[5] he consumed Tea approximately five to six times daily.

Dietary habits were irregular, including Adhyashana (eating before digestion of the complete meal) Vishamashana (irregular eating patterns) Malabaddhta was present & he also had the habit of diwaswapna. Patient reported prolonged exposure to Sunlight as well as frequent exposure to Cold wind. Psychologically he is of Sukshma swabhav.

Clinical Findings

Since swithra is clinically correlated with Vitiligo, Swithra is Thridoshaja kushta with predominant of Vata-Pitta involvement affecting Rakta, Mamsa, Medha dhatu presenting as depigment patches without discharge. The patches are whitish in colour 2 in number.

Diagnostic Assessment: Based on clinical findings diagnosis was established as Swithra in modern science lakshanas like Twak varna nasha, Shweta varna mandala, Kandu rahita, Asrava bhava, Shweta roma, Mandala vridhhi, Vivarna twak etc the case was diagnosed as Swithra.

Intervention & Timeline

Serial no	Procedure	Medicines	Dose
1	Samshodhana	PTG Ghrita + Anulomaka taila	5ml+5ml with 100ml of hot water (BF) 1-0-1x 15days internally
2	Amapachana & Samshamana	Arogyavardini vati	1-0-1(AF) X1 month
		Tiktamrita 500mg cap	1-0-1 (AF) X 1month
		Bakuchi 500mg cap	1-0-1 (AF) X 1month
3	Bahirparimarjana	Bakuchi lepa ^[6] Vencose gel (external application)	Lepa with Gomutra X 15days (morning) Night X 15 days

RESULTS

Before treatment

After treatment

Before treatment

After treatment

After 15 days of treatment: Hyperpigmentation developed over the glabellar lesion followed by desquamation. Gradual restoration of normal skin colour observed. Slower response over the lip region due to absence of hair follicles, which are reservoirs of melanocytes. Mild bullae formation occurred over the lips, likely due to the Tikshna nature of Gomutra and the delicate (Sukshma, Mridu) nature of lip tissue, resulting in prolonged healing.

DISCUSSION

Panchatikta Guggulu Ghrita pacifies Pitta and purifies Rakta, while Eranda Taila mitigates Vata and induces Mridu Virechana, facilitating elimination of vitiated Doshas and promoting Anulomana. The combination assists in Srotoshodhana and enhances drug delivery to Twak Dhatu.

Bakuchi contains psoralen, isopsoralen, bakuchiol, bavachinin, and corylin, which exhibit antioxidant and melanocyte-stimulating properties. These compounds enhance melanin synthesis and demonstrate immunomodulatory effects, from an Ayurvedic perspective, Bakuchi alleviates Kapha Avarana and stimulates Bhrajaka Pitta, promoting repigmentation. Arogyavardhini Vati acts as Rakta-Dushti-Hara, Kushta-Hara, and Srotovishodhana while improving Agni and metabolic function.

Pathya Ahara-Vihara^[7] and daily yoga practice (20 minutes) were advised to reduce stress and support systemic balance.^[8]

CONCLUSION

The increasing incidence of Vitiligo may be associated with Ahitakara Ahara-Vihara, Manasika factors, and genetic predisposition (Kulaja Vruttanta). Early-stage Switra (Nava, Alpa Pramana) responds effectively to combined Shodhana and Shamana therapies.

Adherence to Pathya-Apathya principles, lifestyle modification, and yoga significantly enhances therapeutic outcomes.^[9] Anatomically, lips are lined externally by skin and internally by mucosa. The vermilion area has melanocytes and vessels, but is deficit in hair, sweat glands, and salivary glands. Lip lesions may demonstrate delayed repigmentation due to absence of hair follicles and reduced melanocyte reservoirs. Caution should be exercised while applying Teekshna lepa to delicate areas in order to prevent adverse reactions.^[10]

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